

THE NEUTRALITY OF STATE CIVIL APPARATUS IN GENERAL ELECTIONS, REVIEWED FROM A HUMAN RIGHTS PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

The neutrality of civil servants (ASN) in political activities is regulated by several regulations. On the one hand, ASN as citizens have human rights, including the right to freedom of association, assembly, and expression. However, on the other hand, as state officials, ASN cannot fully exercise these rights. The absence of civil servants (ASN) in practical politics, or from running for office in national or regional elections, is an important step to ensure the neutrality and integrity of ASN. ASN neutrality is necessary to ensure that public services are not influenced by personal or group political interests, so that administrative decisions can be made objectively and fairly. This research uses a normative legal method, also known as doctrinal research. The results show that every ASN is impartial to any form of influence or interest. In this case, there are restrictions on ASN political rights under Law Number 5 of 2014 concerning the State Civil Apparatus that do not violate human rights as stipulated in the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. These regulations constitute a legal consequence for a civil servant having a public service relationship with the government. When someone decides to become a civil servant, they must be prepared to follow and comply with existing regulations.

Keywords: *Civil Servants, Human Rights, Neutrality.*